

WOMEN IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENCE AND EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN: OPPORTUNITIES AND PROSPECTS

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Abstract. *This article reflects on the possibilities and prospects of women living in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan and finding their place in the development of science and education.*

Keywords: *science and education, Uzbek women, innovative processes, quality of education, role of women in education.*

In the years of independence, the reforms implemented in the Republic are at the center of man and his interests. The ultimate goal of all changes was to increase the welfare of the population. Since 2017, the country has entered a new stage of its development in all areas. A new era of large-scale restructuring and reforms has begun in all spheres. The main focus was to solve issues and problems of people's interests that have matured for many years. In particular, one of the important innovations in the history of modern Uzbekistan is the development of the social sphere, science, and education. Also, the issue of expanding the participation of women in this field has come to the fore.

In today's world, it is impossible to imagine the development of any field without innovative ideas and scientific achievements. The greatest wealth of Uzbekistan is the great intellectual and spiritual potential of the people, among the women among the people. On the initiative of the head of state, the large-scale work on improving the education and science system in the republic has become one of the country's socio-political priorities.

On this basis, in today's rapidly developing society, wide opportunities are being created for women who are active in every field or their team. Science and education have found their place with such progress and have already opened their doors for women. It is even impossible to imagine the development of science and education without the participation of women today.

Today, the role of intelligent women in higher education, their activities, and the regular implementation of new generation textbooks, manuals and tools, will naturally increase the quality and efficiency of education. The process of globalization cannot be imagined without intelligent women. And it is natural that it will be difficult to achieve the intended field of activity and the intended perspective. However, thanks to the achievement of independence, the women of Uzbekistan gained true equality. Although those who made a worthy contribution to the field of science were few at first, the attention and recognition given by the state in recent years played a big role in the expansion of their ranks.

In the development of our country, important work has been done to increase the role of women working in the education system in the construction of the state and society, to determine their socio-political activity, initiative, leadership, and professional skills. For example, many women scientists who have been contributing to the improvement of the higher education system

and the development of science in Uzbekistan have been awarded with prestigious state awards. All their actions in the field of science and education have been taken into account and they have been receiving appropriate incentives.

In conclusion, it can be said that the attitude and attention to women and girls in Uzbekistan, in particular, to intellectuals and women scientists, has risen to the state level, and the basis of fundamental changes in their activities has been the result of the wishes implemented in the republic. It is not a secret to anyone that on the direct initiative of the head of state, new aspects of these reforms, more appropriate aspects for the peace and well-being of the country are being developed. In addition, priority tasks such as attention to the development of science, further development of the personnel training system, training of qualified specialists in the field are increasing day by day. Ensuring the place and participation of women in such processes, creating the necessary conditions for them, is constantly being paid attention to. And after that, we can say that this attention will not be continuous, as it has been until now.

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